

INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

Zhoraboyeva Iroda¹

Bozorboyeva Nilufar²

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7875991>

Abstract: This article examines and analyzes the history of bilingualism, the importance of bilingualism in world linguistics, the views of linguists on it, its role in intercultural relations, issues of modern bilingualism, bilingualism in the works of Tahir Malik.

Keywords: bilingualism, bilinguals, bilingualism issues intercultural communication, dialectal and international interface.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that language connections concepts expressive from the terms one is bilingualism. Bilingualism (bilingualism) is to communicate freely in two languages, to be bilingual. means Two in the language mutually communicative to the relationship introductory persons scholars is considered If we focus on the origin of this term, III-II BC centuries, the Romans conquered Iberia (present-day Spain) and Gaul (present-day France). This is it in the regions local language - Latin bilingualism to the body will come.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

In the conditions of mass bilingualism, some types of interface affect the language system can lead to change. In this situation, scientists believe that the regional differentiation of the language is ethnic dialect surface coming can that they count. Interface two to the group: dialectal interface and international interface types separate to the goal according to Dialectal the second subcode unit in the process of communicating through one subcode of the interface language carrier use as a result emerges:

- Come on, come on, my children. Sit down. (Z. p. 78) // - Wow, Savil ! he said wrinkled - His father took the money while he was still alive why does he send it to his pooch? (Z. p. 159) International interface two national of the tongue from intervention harvest will be For example, Uzbek-Russian bilingualism in the following passage let's see can:

- read, i this another without hearing Did you know? Poka i i am all za oil sketch _ You are a student . Tak chto , study know! (Z. p. 93)

Here, some types of interface do not occur in dialectal interface, some of them while activity note reach must In particular, this in the sentence Tashkent dialect used we will see: - Me I'm sorry . Now his brothers I call (Sh. III t p. 159).

Turkish-Russian bilingualism of learning main aspects one contact incoming changes resulting from interaction at all stages of languages, first of all, is the study of changes in all stages of Turkic languages, because it is between languages mutually in effect turkish languages more is variable. Turkish-Russian two language as a result the most significant changes turkish in the syntax of languages happened will give.

RESEARCH THE RESULT

Some parts of the basic language stages are very significantly influenced by bilingualism will change. To them lexicon, mainly his science, politics, economy and ideology with depends terminological part and each different abstract to concepts special lexicon includes: - Me lawyer _ what for me inside won't you? - said brown hat a guy

... The prosecutor from Moscow is interrogating. They are not bringing our prosecutors closer. (VO. 8-p.)

In the above sentences, the words that served to enrich the Uzbek language lexically we can see. Not only Russian and French terms such as lawyer, prosecutor applied in our linguistics, but also globally. Foreign like hat and Moscow as a result of adding the suffix -li to the words, it became a Turkic word from Moscow. One in other words, bilingualism refers to the development of intercultural communication and communication between languages serves. Russian and another significant of languages effect in Turkish literary languages each different to styles special lexical-grammatical of means in use it seems From him except in languages internal of means activation, the first queue dialect and live speech lexicon, doublets and differences in the stylistic use of synonymous, lexical and grammatical lines, etc at the expense of it has been.

Bilingualism and Russian language deep to be studied as a result turkish literary of languages improvement and enrichment of stylistic features in them, in particular, a new rhythm in the poetic style and the use of metric, new poetic forms and the activation of classical poetic laws issues like: I went to Balbesing's house. I talked to the old lady. I started a criminal case, and I'm sorry. After all, a wedding in a month! Da, mejdu prochem, do until the wedding the house in the name of Balbes passes. If he does not pass, his son it rots in prison. (Z. p. 114)

Uzbek and Tajik of their peoples centuries during one in the area side by side living that they came this of languages lexical-semantic to the structure too own effect showed. Of this as a result Uzbek-Tajik bilingualism to the body came That's it separately to emphasize ok lexical-semantic effect wide spread out if both phonetic as an effect to the eye obvious thrown away does not stand. Therefore, the main attention of researchers is focused on the phonetic effect, interlanguage lexical-semantic effect out of consideration outside the rest Uzbek and Tajik languages two linguistic "...living in Bukhara, Samarkand, Ferghana Valley regions Tajik language has similarities and typological closeness with Uzbek language at various linguistic levels. Tajik of the language northern in dialects "felro from the barn" phrase – "Bitter take out",

"Anger take out" in the sense of is applied. This is it in the example Tajik and Uzbek model joined and came to the form of "to extract the verb". He looks at the example of the work of the writer Tahir Malik as for: "The guest watched his actions closely. Although he is bitter because of his rudeness, the secret is rich did not give, he looked at the host"(T.6-p.), "During the years together, he felt Asadbek's anger bringing angry things did a lot. (Sh. IV t., p. 86

DISCUSSION

Tajik in the language "injury" verb the meaning expressed is in Uzbek language "to break" and "lightning" of verbs meaning right will come An example for: "My bone breaking you sent, it seems that it hurts"(T. p. 119), "The father of enthusiasm his leg as a child breaking did you get either congenital lameness The secret does not know you don't care can't walk." (T. p. 216)

Current contacts of the Uzbek language with related and non-related languages, bilingualism and it with depends events research to do Uzbek linguists standing in front of him the most important current from problems is one. Uzbek in linguistics language relations, their to each other to the effect dedicated special theoretical affairs not created. This while language in the field bilingualism and is motivated to carry out work related to the concept of interference.

Two there is also a collection of articles on various issues of linguistics and multilingualism being them bilingualism, its types, historical roots, language interference, its essence, to bilingualism relationship issues like illuminated.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the Uzbek language has wide possibilities exists and in it the role of bilingualism is incomparable. To the development of communication and communication between cultures bilingualism also contributes greatly. The proof of this is the example of the works of Tahir Malik above we have considered. In the next stages of linguistics, the issues of bilingualism are both theoretical and practical to be studied in terms of to the goal according to

References:

1. Rosenzweig V. Yu. Yazykovye contact – Leningrad: Science, 1972.
2. Linguistichesky encyclopedic dictionary. – Moscow: Bolshaya Rossiyskaya encyclopedia, 2002.
3. Rastorgueva V.S. Opyt sravnitel'nogo Izucheniya Tajik gossip. – Moscow: Science. 1964.
4. Hakimov MX Uzbek in the language of the text pragmatic interpretation. Ph.D. diss. – Tashkent: 2001.
5. Malik T. Satan. 5 volumes, Volume 3. - Tashkent: East, 2006
6. Malik T. Satan. 5 Vol Volume 4. – Tashkent: East, 2009
7. Malik T. wow my mother – Tashkent: New century generation, 2015
8. Malik T. Oppression. – Tashkent: East, 2016
9. Malik T. Convulsion. – Tashkent: East, 2012